

Fabric Hand Evaluation Based on PhabrO meter

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Abstract: The first step in any performance review is to break down a large number of items into smaller, more homogenous, more akin groups. Any scientific research begins with classification or sorting, and it is only within a group of similar items that a valid comparison of product quality can be made. This paper is the first to propose a new criterion, fabric linear, density, for classifying fabrics. This parameter's elicitation and validation are described in detail. As obvious as it may seem, there are currently no practical methods for measuring the drape of cloth. Limited repeatedly and low sensitivity limit the usefulness of a few existing devices like the CusickDrapemeter. In this work, the PhabrOmeter and fabric linear density are used to offer a more efficient alternative to fabric drape testing. These principles, procedures, and findings were gleaned from the actual testing of 40 different textiles.

Keywords: Fabric, CusickDrapemeter, PhabrOmeter

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Introduction

To the consumer's visual sense, textile fabric's visual features reflect a distinct subset of sensory properties. These aesthetic features include things like fabric drape, surface condition, and sheen, as well as the ability of the fabric to recover from wrinkles, maintain its surface, and resist stains. It's easier to express these traits as "fabric attributes" rather than "fabric properties" like fabric weight and fabric strength since these terms are more often used. Such fabric sensory qualities are undeniable in their value. It's difficult to believe that someone would purchase a textile item without first inspecting it. This means that a new textile product's success is largely dependent on its ability to appeal to consumers' senses. One of the sensory qualities we examine in this research is the measurement of cloth drape. The phrase "fabric drape" (plural "fabric formability") is used to define the shape or profile of the fabric when it is held at the center or edge, as in curtains, a tablecloth, or a skirt covering an item.

Drape is one of the most difficult characteristics to evaluate because it relies heavily on human judgment, which is difficult to replicate and repeat, lagging behind the industry's need for quick product development and short product turnover time, both of which are becoming increasingly important in the apparel market.

Because of this close link, all of the aforementioned fabric characteristics, such as hand and drape, as well as wrinkle recovery, may be evaluated with the same device. As a consequence, various efforts to develop commercially feasible equipment for assessing these fabric properties have been made throughout the years. "Cantilever" and "loop" are two of Pierce's sample forms for analyzing bending resistance as "strictly an indication of the drape of the cloth." Several current AATCC and ASTM standards tests reflect such approaches to textile chemistry. According to Chu et al 2012.'s research, "two-dimensional distortion tests are incapable of discriminating between drape and pepperness." This implies that a piece of fabric with the same bend qualities as paper may be chosen, but it is unlikely that paper would drape as well. Cusick, Hearse, and an exhaustive. were able to extensively study the subject's previous research with the aid of Cusick, Hearse, and an exhaustive. When it comes to predicting the drape of knitted textiles, multiple regression analysis has been utilized to test the validity of parameters such as stiffness, shear, and extensibility as well as structural factors such as fabric weight, thickness, and density. Static and dynamic draping of textiles was the topic of many investigations. The draping behaviour of multi-layer fabrics has also been studied using digital image dispensation. The difficult problem of the theoretical mould of cloth drape marvels has, as predicted, sparked a lot of discussions.

When it comes to fabric drapes, researchers believe that shear resistance, not only bending resistance, is more important. We also identify that paper and cloth are illustrious by their fleece characteristics.

Research for a healthier fabric drape exam instrument continues to this study; few commercially accessible devices exist, including the Cloth Curtain Tester (also recognized as the Cusick Drape meter or Chu technique) that uses a paper trace to trace the shadow of an actual, draped fabric. However, because of its flaws. This test has not been extensively used, even in the United States. Fabric drape testing is a critical gap that has to be filled rapidly, yet there is no US standard for it. Any user of the Cusick Drape meter will quickly recognize the following issues:

1. It is difficult to get consistent findings when testing the same sample more than once, and the Chu advocated using additional test copies when this was the case. "A fair number is five in each direction, warp and filling" Considering that textiles are anisotropic, one may ask, "Why not?"
2. Only a considerable variation in fabric drape may be observed because of the low sensitivity.
3. The testing procedure is lengthy and slow.
4. As a consequence, test findings are less reliable, both in terms of replication and in terms of their underlying physical significance.
5. A 30-cm-diameter sample size is needed. If the warp and filler directions call for five each, that's a lot of cloth to ask for in many circumstances.

The Cusick Drape meter has gone through numerous versions in an attempt to overcome some of the design problems, but none of these iterations has resulted in a commercial model being widely used by industry. Imaging analysis has been utilized in the test; however, it can only improve data interpretation and does little to address the test principles' intrinsic flaws.

The Japanese Kawabata fabric-hand system makes the most efforts to address overall linkages between fabric sensory characteristics and mechanical attributes (better known in Japan as the KES system). Figure 1 illustrates the findings of Pan and his colleagues' PhabrOmeter fabric testing equipment, which they developed and commercialized in 1983. Pan and his colleagues invented and marketed the PhabrOmeter fabric testing system in 1983. When compared to Japan's KES approach, there is no effort to evaluate particular fabric qualities (such as bending and compression) that are thought to be connected with fabric sensory features. As an alternative, this instrument is based on an earlier proposal for fabric extraction and incorporates significant modifications to produce complete test findings. An algorithmic process will then produce several metrics, such as a Comparative Hand Worth, the fabric's gentleness, smoothness, stiffness, etc.. PhabrOmeter users may also refer to an AATCC standard test technique, AATCC TM202

“Hardware for the PhabrOmeter Model 3.”

“The fabric sample extraction process.”

Cloth hand and drapeability have long been shown to be intertwined. We should look into the possibility of using the PhabrOmeter to measure fabric drape since the fabric sample undergoes a forced curtain with a complicated but low-pressure condition, as shown in Figure, during the extraction process. PhabrOmeter's "historicization" of the measuring procedure and elimination of the sample maneuvering effect, an issue sternly ailing the findings of the Cusick Drape meter is an additional benefit of employing it for fabric drape tests.

“Fabric weight” (weight/area) and “fabric thickness” (thickness) are used in the formula W/T . (length). To avoid this, the second criterion is that both “fabric weight” and thickness consume to have a direct effect on the outcome. Alternatively, a new parameter may be defined.

$$\lambda = W \times T$$

Changing the weight or thickness of the cloth will have the same effect on the value, therefore both conditions are satisfied. $(\text{Weight/Length}) = (\text{Weight/Length}) = (\text{Linear Density})$. For the three numbers W , T , and, the usual potential ranges are shown in Table 1, which includes the vast majority of commercial fibrous sheets.

FAST-2								
warp bending lengthC (mm)	Weft bending length C (mm)	square meterg/m ²	warp bending stiffness (uN·m)	Weft bending stiffness (uN·m)	Warp bending length C (mm)	Weft bending length C (mm)	warp bending stiffness (uN·m)	Weft bending stiffness (uN·m)
67.0	60.5	132	389.4640	286.7537	32.63	29.46	44.9836	33.12043
58.0	52.5	130	248.8263	184.5399	28.25	25.57	28.73977	21.3146
56.0	62.5	132	227.4087	316.1426	27.27	30.44	26.266	36.51488
52.5	55.5	138	195.8962	231.4339	25.57	27.03	22.62627	26.73092
53.0	51.0	138	201.5467	179.5803	25.81	24.84	23.27891	20.74176
55.5	55.0	138	231.4339	225.2351	27.03	26.79	26.73092	26.01495
59.0	64.5	140	282.0675	368.5328	28.73	31.41	32.57917	42.56602
57.5	53.5	138	257.3663	207.3048	28.00	26.05	29.72614	23.94398
63.0	54.5	139	340.9616	220.7361	30.68	26.54	39.38151	25.4953
60.0	61.0	134	283.9406	298.3756	29.22	29.71	32.79551	34.46277
58.0	65.0	132	252.6544	355.6174	28.25	31.66	29.18192	41.07427
57.0	62.5	133	241.6269	318.5376	27.76	30.44	27.90822	36.79151

It's still debatable whether or not it's a good idea to categorize all items by splitting their value in half, as there's no way to prove that the value is spread equally over the full scope. When it comes to the potential fabric ranges, it's reasonable to assume a normal distribution of rather than the extremes or outliers. Table 2 shows the results of the alliance based on this deliberation, as used by the PhabrOmeter at the moment.

GROUP A	SUPER LIGTH (S)	LIGHT	MEDIUM	HEAVY
λ (Mg/cm	<280	280-1200	<1201-3340	<3340

9	26	9	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	horizontal Num-	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6
	ber of tests (times)	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m
		m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m
1	31	8	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	15	5	1	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	12	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	27	9	3	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	17	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	15	6	3	3	2	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	13	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	16	4	3	2	2	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	33	7	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

3

portrait Number
of tests (times)

		0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0
1		m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m
		m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m
17		4	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	33	7	3	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	24	4	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	0
4	27	7	9	7	2	4	2	0	1	1
5	17	11	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	23	7	5	2	2	0	0	0	0	0
7	22	9	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	20	8	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0

14	2	5	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3
Horizontal	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m
	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m
Number of tests												
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
(times												
2	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	14	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	8	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	8	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	6	3	2	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
9	9	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

4. Measurement by PhabrOmeter

PhabrOmeter's fabric removal approach models real-world fabric behavior and closely mimics the testing procedure, which involves putting a fabric sample through a forced drape while being subjected to a variety of pressures. The PhabrOmeter is consequently recommended as a tool for measuring cloth drape. More theoretical background on the idea is available for those who want to avoid repetition. PhabrOmeter's high levels of repeatability, sensitivity, and speed make it a strong contender to take the place of some of the currently used, but ineffective, test techniques for measuring cloth drape.

A conventional cutter was used to cut the samples into a 100 cm² circular form and fasten them to a sample holder in PhabrOmeter. Before using the instrument, you'll be prompted by the computer to enter information about the fabric's weight and thickness, which will be used to determine its linear density. A density group has been given to the sample for further testing and analysis, as shown in Table 3. A variety of sample parameters may be entered by the user, allowing the computer to do finer grouping as required. The drape coefficient of the cloth will be shown or stored as a data file when the sample is evaluated. The PhabrOmeter user handbook [46] provides further information on testing and data production.

5. "Data Analysis"

Measurements of the drape yielded the following information (Table 5): Dimensions:

Equation (2) yields the following fabric linear density values:

Cotton Inc.'s DrapeCB, based on Cusick data and ISO 9073-9:2008 Option B;

UCD's DrapeUA Cusick data, based on ISO 9073-9:2008 Option A;

For Option A data, DrapeUAB was corrected to Choice B; and for PhabrOmetershutter data, DrapePh was corrected to Option B data.

2-1	1	1.38	0.25	21°C	65%
2-1-w	1	1.38	0.25	21°C	65%
2-2	1	1.38	0.25	21°C	65%
2-2-w	1	1.38	0.25	21°C	65%
2-3	1	1.38	0.24	21°C	65%
2-3-w	1	1.38	0.24	21°C	65%
average value		1.38	0.25		
3-1	1	1.40	0.25	21°C	65%
3-1-w	1	1.40	0.25	21°C	65%
3-2	1	1.38	0.25	21°C	65%
3-2-w	1	1.38	0.25	21°C	65%
3-3	1	1.39	0.25	21°C	65%
3-3-w	1	1.39	0.25	21°C	65%
average value		1.39	0.25		
4-1	1	1.34	0.23	21°C	65%
4-1-w	1	1.34	0.23	21°C	65%
4-2	1	1.32	0.22	21°C	65%
4-2-w	1	1.32	0.22	21°C	65%
4-3	1	1.33	0.22	21°C	65%
4-3-w	1	1.33	0.22	21°C	65%
average value		1.33	0.22		

“Fabric SAMPLE Classifier”

PhabrOmeter now uses the fabric classifier, which was investigated here to demonstrate its efficacy. Fabric weight W and thickness T are shown in Figure 3 in relation to energy, while the area under the extraction curve (energy) is shown in Figure 2 as a representation of the energy necessary to extract a sample via a testing ring and determined using

PhabrOmeter for all 40 textiles. Increasing fabric weight or thickness increases fabric compaction density during extraction, hence increasing extraction energy. This is evident in both figures, which show that both exhibit the same tendency toward the outcome. More comprehensive than fabric weight or thickness is the fabric linear density, which, as demonstrated, has a $r = 0.86$ association with the extraction energy.

As shown in Table 6, DrapePh and DrapeUA are drapability coefficients of the UCD fabric determined using the PhabrOmeter and Cusick techniques, respectively, and may be used to compare this linear density to other fabric properties. RHV is the relative fabric hand value where #26 (RHV = 0) was selected as a rho. Energy is the fabric extraction energy. The following should be mentioned in the table:

In terms of DrapePh, DrapeUA, and RHV, correlations are quite strong.

It is just the linear density that has a meaningful correlation with extraction energy.

Here are a few hypotheses you may want to consider. When it comes to characterizing how a fabric is extracted, intrinsic material qualities like extraction energy and linear density are linked to each other and are less linked to the other leas DrapePH and DrapeUA are more extrinsic, and apiece is significantly associated by the others.

5.2. "Comparison of Drape Data"

Samples number 9 and number 10 did not have drapability data, so n = 38 samples were used to compare to the Cusick drapability data from Cotton Inc. Cotton Inc. versus UCD data on Cusick drapes are shown in Figure 5. With a correlation coefficient of 0.95, there is a high degree of agreement. Data from ISO 9073-9:2008 Options A and B, used by UCD and Cotton Inc., appear to be in agreement. For Cotton Inc.'s purposes, this data appears to be either too high or too low. The single knitted Inlay that appears to be an outlier, #33, has an irregular drapability (for UCD).

However, in Figure 6, instead of using the original UCD drapability data, we use the corrected version. If you exclude #33, you can see that the two sets of data have a very good linear association. There was a significant drop in association from $r = 0.97$ to $r = 0.77$ as a result of the inclusion of #33 in the dataset. Cotton Inc. and UCD Cusick information appear to be reliable, and data alteration does not appear to improve things significantly. These statistics, despite their shortcomings, may be used as aorientation when compared to the PhabrOmeterblind data for at smallest the 40 materials listed above.

PhabrOmeter-based drape data DrapePh is compared to Cusick screen data for the 38 Fiber Inc. DrapeCB textiles in Figure 7. Both sets of data show a $r = 0.88$ (or $r = 0.91$ if #39 is excluded) correlation, demonstrating that the PhabrOmeter drape data and the Cusick drape data accurately describe cloth drape performance. According to the data in Figure 8, which shows the PhabrOmeter drape Ph compared to the UCD drape data DrapeUA for all 40 textiles with a r of 0.89 (or 0.91 when you exclude fabric #39), the same conclusion can be reached from those findings.

Both fabrics have a lot of give to them. PhabrOmeter testing eliminates the issue of fabric curl, a common occurrence with the Cusick technique.

5.3. Fabric Drapes Measuring Variables Cusick drapes data according to ISO 9073-9:2008 option A or option B is consistent; PhabrOmeter has been shown to accurately measure fabric drapes qualities. Cusick test recommends using a different sample size for certain items, and fabric curl is a common issue. For PhabrOmeter, none of these issues are of any significance. Other considerations are listed in the paragraphs that follow.

5.3.1. The Effect of Grouping As one of the remaining challenges, is it better to utilize all 40 textiles as a group to test/comparison fabric drapes conduct, or break them down into subcategories to do so in more depth? When all textiles are divided into smaller groups, the test findings are more likely to agree, as is to be anticipated. This also increases the level of cooperation among all parties involved, thus a compromise is ideal. Table 3 lists the three groups of fabric linear density that we utilized to examine the effect of grouping.

For Group 2, we utilized just 27 light textiles (of the 40 total), and for Group 3, we used completely 40 fabrics in a solitary group (11 Medium and heavy fabrics).

A total of two textiles (#26 and #38) in the Super light Group and one (#31) in the Heavy Cluster were excluded from contrast.

To investigate the federation effect related with line density, we tested the shade data using PhabrOmeter.

A comparison of draping data was performed.

IT shows the drapesPh and fabric linear density when altogether 40 fabrics are grouped together. An unimpressive correlation of $r = 0.197$ recommends that comparing the drapes behaviors of various kinds of materials shouldn't be

attempted. Group 2 (27 light textiles alone) has a r value of 0.696 in Figure 9b, while Group 3 (11 average and heavy fabrics) has a r value of 0.901 in Figure 9c, after being separated into smaller groups. This means that grouping textiles according to their linear density does, in fact, increase the comparability of performance.

Sample name	thick-ness)	Thermal resistance(m ² ·K/W)	Cro valu clo	Heat transfer coefficient W/(m ² ·K)	Thermal conductivity W/(m·K)
1-1	0.22	0.01493	0.09635	66.963	0.01473
1-2	0.23	0.01925	0.12419	51.949	0.01195
1-3	0.23	0.01802	0.11627	55.487	0.01276
average value	0.23	0.01740	0.11227	58.133	0.01315
2-1	0.25	0.01687	0.10885	59.269	0.01482
2-2	0.24	0.02128	0.13732	46.984	0.01128
2-3	0.24	0.02045	0.13194	48.899	0.01174
average value	0.24	0.01953	0.12604	51.717	0.01261
3-1	0.25	0.02508	0.16179	39.875	0.00997
3-2	0.24	0.02591	0.16714	38.601	0.00926
3-3	0.24	0.01636	0.10555	61.122	0.01467
average value	0.24	0.02245	0.14483	46.533	0.01130
4-1	0.23	0.02037	0.13140	49.097	0.01129
4-2	0.22	0.02240	0.14451	44.646	0.00982
4-3	0.22	0.02360	0.15226	42.373	0.00932
average value	0.22	0.02212	0.14272	45.372	0.01014

5.3.2. The Effect of Building Type on the Design The fabric building kinds, i.e., woven, knit, or non-woven, are often employed as a grouping criterion. Thirteen woven and twenty-seven knits make up the 40 textiles. Correlation analysis was used once more to see if grouping based on construction improved the results. As a result of this grouping based on construction, we had to employ Cusick blind data DrapeUA to compare the varied fabric linear density values.

Figure 8 shows that the connection between drape data obtained using Cusick and PhabrOmeter systems is $r = 0.89$ when all 40 textiles are grouped together. In the case of the woven group, this connection was $r = 0.819$, but in the case of the knit group, it was just $r = 0.785$. In other words, grouping textiles based on edifice type doesn't seem to increase the uniformity.

5.3.3. Fiber Kinds and their influence the different kinds of fibers may also be used as a basis for classification. Thus, the 40 textiles are divided into three groups: pure cotton cotton blends and man-made fibers.(Five polyester and one1 rayon). Using Cusick and PhabrOmeter drape data, the links are: $r = 0.838$ for unadulterated cotton; $r = 0.554$ for cotton

blends; and $r = 0.545$ for synthetics. That is to say, categorizing based on the type of fiber does not appear to be an option here either.

Next, we looked at textiles that are notoriously difficult to test because of their inherent looseness, limpidity, and elasticity. In order to address the difficulties of challenging direction and example side, which proved to be additional relevant, we investigated the possible causes of such test mistakes. PhabrOmeter's round specimens "isotropize" the specimens, reducing anisotropy. As a guide, below are the actions taken:

From the 40 fabric set, choose the 18 loosest, limpiest, and most stretchy textiles.

The directionality of the Cusick screen test is not anmatter for PhabrOmeter, hence follow choice A in ISO 9073-9:2008.

At zero, 45, and 90 degrees to the instrument width, the sample is aligned in three separate locations.

Verify the front and back of the product.

Testing direction and specimen side have been shown to have a significant influence on test outcomes. A polyester jersey with yarns twisted alternately in S and Z directions, as shown in Figure 10a, has a drape coefficient of about half that of a cotton t-shirt, at 10.66 (0). Face and rear sides of the same sample exhibit a considerable variance, with a maximum difference of 16.774 (face) at 90 degrees and 15.754 (back) (back). For Sample #23, a plated jersey made of 37% cotton and 63% acetate, little direction impact was seen, but there was a considerable side effect.

(a)

“There are three types of data shown in Figure 9: (a) PhabrOmeter Drape data and Linear Density ($n = 40$); (b) PhabrOmeter Drape data and Linear Density ($n = 27$ for only light weight); (c) PhabrOmeter Drape data and Linear Density (only $n = 11$ for medium weight).”

“Directional and side effects for Sample #36; (b) directional and side effects for Sample #37”

Sample #33, on the other hand, had a strange drape throughout our tests. When we first ran the Cusick drape test, we got a result of 20.6. Our second round of testing for the directional effect yielded 35.4, 34.54 and 33.61 values for the three testing directions (0, 45°, and 90°) that were significantly different from the first round's results. We were able to confirm the accuracy of all the data after thoroughly reviewing our testing processes. We discovered a few possibilities for the problem by looking at the cloth itself:

Due to the fact that it is a single-knit Inlay, #33 is quite unstable. Inadvertent modification of the fabric structure might lead to testing variances if it is not handled or kept with particular care throughout the procedure.

Sample #33 has a fabric stretch of 1852.4 percent. Because of this, determining if a sample has any residual deformation from past straining that has resulted in property changes is difficult. Using the Cusick method, sample #33 displays a significant curl.

Results

Our results from the Cusick Drapemeter (ISO) cloth drape test support the validity of both Option A and Option B. Using PhabrOmeter for measuring cloth drape qualities was shown to be a more reliable and effective strategy in this research, since it is fast, sensitive, and repeatable (4,9). Additionally, it contains the following features. A force applied at the sample center "isotropizes" the measuring procedure, reducing the variance caused by fabric directionality or anisotropies, by cutting the specimens into circular shapes and extracting them throughout the test.

When samples are forced to drape, the recommended sample sizes in the Cusick test become unnecessary.

It is no longer need to worry about fabric curl when using the PhabrOmeter approach since the sample is actively compressed during testing.

However, if studying fabric directionality or curling is a priority, this approach will fall short because the Cusick approach fails to account for these issues.

To ensure that the drape test results are consistent, the face of the test subject should be recognized and documented. Side-by-side comparisons can yield very different outcomes. Likening the drape behaviors of various fabric kinds is not acceptable, and such comparisons may be more useful if they are divided into more homogenous groups, e.g., using fabric linear density. Once in the same group determined by fabric linear density, additional categorization based on fabric structure and fiber kinds is possible, if required. However, our findings suggest that further separation does not lead to any further improvement.

Conclusion

By definition, the fabric linear density established in this work represents the impact of both fabric weight and thickness on withdrawal using PhabrOmeter, which is tied carefully to a series of fabric parameters and straightforward to compute. Our findings show that comparing the performance of textiles based on their linear density is a worthwhile endeavor. The fabric linear density does not conflict with or replace other important characteristics, such as fabric weave and fiber type, according to the validation reported in this work. It is thus recommended to be utilized as a main fabric classifier more broadly.

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